

Synthesis and Bioactive Nature of some 2-Pyridones

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1-(Aminophenyl)-2-pyridones are useful central nervous system depressant¹. This prompted us to prepare 1-(heterocyclic)-2-pyridone in which the heterocyclic moiety is a pyridine or a thiazole nucleus (1).

In general these compounds (Table 1) were prepared by the condensation of methylcoumalate (2) with the appropriate heterocyclic amine to form an open-chain Schiff base² (3).

The Schiff base was then cyclised by heating in a basic solution, usually aqueous sodium carbonate. Cyclisation^{3,4} was accompanied by the hydrolysis of ester group, and the acid was isolated by acidification with glacial acetic acid as shown in Scheme 1. The acids thus obtained were converted to the various amides and substituted amides through the intermediate acid chloride which was produced by the addition of thionyl chloride to a suspension of the acid in chloroform or benzene, then the acid chloride was reacted with appropriate amine.

The methyl esters were prepared by saturating at 0° a mixture of the respective acid in methanol with hydrogen chloride gas and then refluxing for several hours.

Scheme 1

Biological activity : In general, little potentially useful activity on the central nervous system was disclosed by the compounds in the series. One possible exception might be compound sl. no 5 (Table 1), which exhibited weak analgesic mg/kg p.o. The oral LD₅₀ in mice was 1 600 (1 280–2 000) mg/kg. Attention is also directed to the compound sl. no 12 which increased femoral and coronary blood flow, the potency being approximately one-fourth that of papaverine. These compounds also induced mild central nervous system stimulation without a corresponding increases in blood pressure.

Experimental

1-(Heterocyclic)pyridine-2(1H)one-5-carboxylic acid (1). **General procedure** : A solution of methyl coumalate (0.2 mol) in ethanol (80 ml) was added rapidly to a stirred solution of appropriate heterocyclic amine (0.2 mol) in ethanol (60 ml). The Schiff base precipitated within 5–30 min. The mixture was allowed to stand overnight, and the resulting solid was washed with ethanol

TABLE I—PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS I*

Sl no	R ₁	R ₂	Yield %	M p ^{**} °C	Procedure
1	2-Thiazolyl	OH	20	264 ^a	1
2	2-Thiazolyl	OCH ₃	40	161 ^b	3
3	2-Thiazolyl	NH ₂	75	268 ^c	2
4	2-Thiazolyl	1-Pyrrolidino	50	204 ^c	2
5	2-Thiazolyl	N(CH ₂ CH ₃) ₂	40	141 ^d	2
6	2-Pyridyl	OH	27	277-78 ^a	1
7	2-Pyridyl	N(CH ₂ CH ₃) ₂	44	149 ^c	2
8	2-Pyridyl	OCH ₃	54	163 ^b	3
9	2-Pyridyl	Pyrrolidino	52	183 ^b	2
10	2-Pyridyl	Morpholino	45	199 ^d	2
11	2-Pyridyl	NH ₂	35	246 ^d	2
12	2-Pyridyl	1-Methyl piperazinyl	45	152 ^b	2
13	2-Pyridyl	Phenyl	40	168 ^a	1
14	2-Pyridyl	3-Pyridyl-amino	48	266 ^b	2

*All compounds gave satisfactory C, H and N analyses.

**Solvent for crystallisation ^aglacial acetic acid, ^bmethanol, ^cethanol, ^disopropanol

The Schiff base (10 g) was added to aqueous sodium carbonate (100 ml). The mixture was heated with stirring at 60–70° for 5–10 min, then cooled to room temperature, filtered and acidified to pH 5 with glacial acetic acid. The solid thus formed was washed with 10% acetic acid, dried in an oven at 100° and recrystallised from glacial acetic acid.

1-[2'-Thiazolyl]pyridin-2(1H)-one-5-carboxylic acid (1): It was obtained as above in 20% yield, m.p. 264°, $\nu_{\max}$ (nujol) 3480, 1680, 1560, 876 and 714 cm^{-1} ; ¹H nmr δ 12.2 (s, 1H), 8.2 (s, 2H), 7.2 (d, 2H), 7.3 (s, 1H), 7.3 (d, 1H), 6.5 (d, 2H).

1-(Heterocyclic)pyridin-2(1H)-one-5-carboxamides (2). *General procedure*:

The acid chloride: To a slurry of the appropriate carboxylic acid (0.05 mol) in dry chloroform (100 ml) at 0–5°, was added thionyl chloride (0.2 mol). After addition, the mixture was allowed to warm spontaneously. A vigorous reaction started at 20–30°

and when the reaction subsided the mixture was refluxed for 10 min. The chloroform and excess thionyl chloride were removed by distillation under reduced pressure. Then two successive additions of dry benzene were made, each followed by distillation under reduced pressure to remove last traces of thionyl chloride.

The carboxamides. Procedure-1: To a slurry of the above acid chloride in dry chloroform (100 ml) was added the respective amine (0.2 mol). The mixture was slowly refluxed for 2 h. The cooled mixture was extracted with 3N HCl. The acid solution was washed with chloroform and then adjusted to pH 8 with sodium carbonate. The resulting solid was washed with water and crystallised from the appropriate solvent.

Procedure-2: The acid chloride, prepared as above was slurried in dry benzene (100 ml) and to the slurry at 10–15° was added the respective amine (0.2 mol). The mixture was refluxed for 5 h, then cooled and filtered. The solid was slurried in water, collected by filtration, washed with water until the washing was colourless, dried at 70° and recrystallised from appropriate solvent.

Procedure-3: The procedure was the same as described for Procedure-2 except that the water slurry of the product was adjusted to pH 10 with 15% aqueous sodium carbonate before filtration.

Methyl ester of 1-(heterocyclic)pyridin-2(1H)-one-5-carboxylic acid (3): A mixture of the respective carboxylic acid (0.02 mol) and methanol (100 ml) was saturated at 0° with HCl gas and then refluxed for 3 h. The methanol and excess hydrogen chloride were removed under reduced pressure. The residue was dissolved in water (50 ml) and the solution adjusted to pH 8 with concentrated ammonium hydroxide. The solid that formed was washed with water, dried and recrystallised from ethanol.

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NOTE

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